

Forensic Fingerprint Evidence in the Age of DNA profiling And Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT: In crime investigation and to identify right culprit forensic fingerprints play a key role. It provides sufficient evidence for individualization of real culprit. Researcher in present Article aimed to highlight not only its importance but also wanted to identify new dimensions of working with Artificial intelligence by using this ancient method of investigation and proving case against accused. Researcher has used doctrinal method to explore and suggest new areas of improvement in this regard. It is concluded by researcher that finger prints are most authentic medium of identifying any criminal and it must be made more efficient by connecting it with Artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Finger Prints, Identification, Artificial Intelligence, Police, Investigation, Criminals, Courts.

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1. Introduction

Fingerprints are characterized by the unique patterns found on the fingertips, consisting of ridges with raised friction and recessed furrows arranged in a regular manner. These patterns are highly valued as evidence in legal settings due to their distinctiveness, unchanging nature, and lasting presence. Their reliability and uniqueness make fingerprint analysis a widely accepted method for individual identification.

Fingerprints exhibit identifiable features across three main dimensions, level 1, level 2, and level 3 characteristics.

Level 1 features encompass broad patterns like loops, whorls, arches, and accidental patterns, defining the macroscopic layout of the print.

Level 2 features delve deeper, focusing on Galton characteristics or minutiae points such as ridge endings, enclosures, bifurcations, hooks, and eyes.

Level 3 features encompass microscopic attributes like ridge details, pores, incipient ridges, warts, creases, scars, and other minute characteristics within the ridges.

Modern fingerprint technology has primarily focused on identifying level 1 and level 2 features, typically requiring 6 to 17 minutiae points for successful recognition, though this number varies by region. However, relying solely on these patterns and minutiae points isn't always sufficient, especially when dealing with fragmented or distorted fingerprints commonly found at crime scenes. These challenges can lead to mismatches and reduced accuracy in fingerprint identification, particularly when dealing with latent fingerprints that require visualization before analysis.

Conventional methods may obscure details and introduce pseudo characteristics, affecting identification accuracy, and techniques such as moulding or inkjet printing can create fake prints that fool minutiae-based matching systems. Addressing these limitations, the permanence and uniqueness of level 3 fingerprint features have gained attention. Locard's work in 1912 showed that as few as 20 to 40 pores can offer reliable personal identification, leading to advancements in algorithms leveraging level 3 features that enhance recognition accuracy.

Combining level 3 features with level 1 and 2 data significantly reduces error rates in matching, and recent studies highlight their utility beyond individualization, offering insights into gender, age, race, and health. Despite their potential, current practices inadequately utilize level 3 details due to visualization challenges, low-quality crime scene prints, and imaging resolutions below the necessary standards.

Efforts are underway to integrate level 3 features into fingerprint recognition and profiling, attracting interest from forensic experts and researchers across disciplines. This mini-review aims to summarize recent advancements in level 3 detail detection, emphasizing reliability assessment, visualization methods, and their potential in various applications such as personal identification, donor profiling, age determination, spoof detection, and even disease diagnosis. Sections will cover feature types, detection techniques (including physical and chemical methods), application scenarios, and future research directions.

Reliability: Opinions differ significantly on what constitutes level 3 features, leading to debates about their reliability. Some consider incipient ridges, warts, creases, and scars as level 3 characteristics because they require microscopic examination for recognition, while others argue they belong to level 2 features due to their visibility without magnification. However, a broader perspective includes micro dimensional attributes such as ridge contour, width (radioscopy), and pore characteristics like shape, size, location, frequency, and interspace (Poros copy) as part of level 3 features.

Since level 2 details alone may not suffice for accurate comparisons, especially with problematic or spoof fingerprints, researchers are exploring the evidential value of level 3 features. However, the reliability of level 3 details is influenced by various factors including donor physical conditions, deposition methods, and storage conditions. Thus, assessing their reliability involves examining reproducibility and persistency across multiple depositions or over time intervals.

Sweat Pores: Sweat pores, located along the papillary ridges, are created by ducts running from the dermis to the epidermis. Locard argued that these pores are unique and permanent, varying from person to person. Generally, sweat pore characteristics include size, shape, location, distribution, frequency, and spacing between pores. Figure 2 provides a visual guide to the typical measurements used in researching sweat pores, highlighting their parameters.

Sweat pores can exhibit various shapes such as square, triangle, round, oval, or irregular. The shape is often assessed by pore size or area, with typical diameters ranging

from 50 to 265 micrometres. The observed size may vary based on deposition or detection methods, deposition pressures, perspiration levels, and individual characteristics of fingerprint donors. Ashbaugh argued against using pore area for individualization without supporting evidence, and research has explored how detection methods influence pore area measurements. For instance, high-quality inked prints showed consistent pore areas, while latent and livescan prints were less accurate in reproducing pore areas. Conversely, Sutton et al.'s study found that pore area measurements in inked fingerprints were inconsistent across different deposition substrates.

2. Literature Review

In 1897 first time in India a fingerprint Bureau was established in that time Calcutta(Kolkata) after approval from council of Governor General committee report that there is need of classification of criminal record by using their fingerprint. In the year 1901 first time fingerprint Bureau was founded in Metropolitan police head quarter Scotland Yard and Sir Edward Richard Henry supervised that development of fingerprint classification system afterward that was named as Henry classification system. In 1905 same system was launched in New York City Police Department.

Identification by fingerprints: there are three characteristics that help in identification of humans by fingerprints. To get clear fingerprint ink pads are useful first of all a pattern of fingerprint will be obtained by dipping fingers on inkpad and pasting on paper. Distinguish the common shapes which appear are arches, loops and whorls. Classify roughness of point features and structure to match and differentiate between fingerprints of two persons, it will be noticed that they are different and then of same individual for at least ten points matching prints are: hands, lip, pattern of teeth, eyes touch pattern, ear shape, vocal sound, shoe prints, and footprints.

Problem Statement: It is observed that presently Forensic experts highlighting AI and DNA profiling more than Fingerprints and in all over the world it is an ignored area of Forensic. Research aimed to highlight importance and its authenticity of Forensic Fingerprint before the world.

3. Methodology

Doctrinal research methodology is used to conduct present research; case laws and research articles are also included in present research.

Aims and Objectives:

To cover gaps of present knowledge.

Fundamental Principles of Fingerprints: Fingerprints are unique in all individuals made of shapes like hills or ridges and valleys or furrows. Fingerprints of all human beings remain the same during lifetime. Fingerprints could not be shattered or damaged even after burning of skin. Twins also have dissimilar/distinct fingerprints. A fingerprint has different patterns i.e. whorl ridge and other patterns which makes it systematic and different¹.

- Fingerprints start forming early during embryo development (starts developing from 10th week of conception/pregnancy).

- Human composition of genes performs a significant role in forming patterns of fingerprints.

- Two characteristics of fingerprints make it most important source of human identification:

- 1.Fingerprints are unique in nature to every human

- 2.It never changed in whole life of individual (except until and unless there wide-ranging harm to the dermal layer)

Terminology

- AFIS/IAFS Integrated Automated Fingerprint Identification System
- NADRA National Database and Registration Authority
- NFSA National forensic science agency
- Real fingerprints embossed on soften substance like wet soil, putty, or candle wax
- Indented or moulded, light (latent print) print
- Concealed fingerprint produced due to transmission of secretions from skin i.e oils and other secretions from human skin on to surface
- Latent print should be highlighted by physical or chemical means

4. Different Shapes and Pattern Found on Finger Print and Used By Expert in Comparing and Matching

<p>65% Loops</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ulnar=60% • Radial=5% 	<p>30% Whorls</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Plain=24% -Central Pocket=2% -Double Loop=4% -Accidental/other=0.01% 	<p>5% Arches</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Plain=4% -Tented=1%
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Arch: is **rarest** category of **fingerprint**. As in whole world population about 5% peoples have this type of Fingerprint. Its lack of cores, lines or deltas makes it unique. An arch has irregular edges that cross from other lines upward in the middle. It is of two types Plain Tented

-ridges enter on one side of the impression and flow out tend to flow out the other side with a rise or wave in the center

Arch

An arch has friction ridges that enter on one side of the finger and cross to the other side while rising upward in the middle. They do NOT have type lines, deltas, or cores.

Types

- Plain
- Tented

Loop

Loop: “in loop one or more of the ridges enter on either side of the impression, re-curve, touch or pass an imaginary line drawn from the delta to the core, and terminate or

tend to terminate on or toward the same side of the impression from whence such ridge or ridges entered" (Smith, J. A., & Johnson 2012) . Loop is of two types:

Radial—Its direction of opening is toward thumb

Ulnar—Its direction of opening is towards small little finger "pinky"

Whorl: It has at least one ridge that makes a complete circuit. It also has two deltas in it. Thumbs having lack of flexibility with this type of whorls indicates extremely Intelligent and genius, exacting, organised and dominating individuals. A hand that has only one or two whorled **fingerprints** shows a bright, organized mind without the desire for perfectionism. Two loops make a double loop.

Accidental Whorl: "It consists of an amalgamation of two separate kinds of patterns with the exception of the plain arch, with two or more deltas or a pattern which possesses some of the requirements for two or more different types or a pattern which conforms to none of the definitions" (Smith, J. A., & Johnson 2012).

Plain Arches, Tented Arches and Spike:

A **plain arch** is just a slight curve; a **tented arch** has a **spike**.

Plain arch and tented arch are the same in structure, only difference is presence of spike in middle.

Spike or "tent"

Delta:- Delta resembles with the Greek letter delta. It indicates the point on friction ridge and point of divergence of to lines.

- Ridge patterns not enough to individualize fingerprints
- Details between ridges
- About 150 different characteristics on average print
- Identify characteristics and the relative number

Latent Prints: these types of prints are not easily visible and could be found at variety of surface and formed due to natural body oils and sweat on the human skin are deposited on other surface. Its detection requires the use of fingerprint detection powder, chemical reagent or use of alternate light source or blue light.

“**Fingerprints** have been developed on porous surfaces (**papers**, etc.) forty years and later after their deposition. On non-porous surfaces, they can also **last** a very **long** time. The nature of the matrix of the latent print will often determine whether it will survive environmental conditions” (Smith, J. A., & Johnson 2012).

Developing Latent Prints: To make latent fingerprints visible, substances that react with the secretions are used. These substances help the fingerprints stand out against the background. Often, multiple attempts and techniques are applied in specific patterns to secure the print.

One common method involves dusting the surface with fine powder, which adheres to the sweat and oils in the fingerprint. This pattern can then be lifted with transparent tape. Surfaces such as tool handles, glass, or doors can be processed this way. Black powder is often used for dusting, and the print is then lifted with clear tape.

Another method is the cyanoacrylate fuming process, also known as the super glue method. This technique enhances latent fingerprints on various objects by creating a hard, whitish deposit where the fingerprint residues are present.

Magnetic powder is another tool for disclosing latent prints, particularly effective on shiny surfaces or plastic bags and containers. For dark and multi-colored surfaces, fluorescent powder and UV lights can be utilized to reveal latent prints.

Ninhydrin is a chemical that reacts with amino acids in the fingerprint to produce a purple color. Silver nitrate reacts with chloride to form silver chloride, which turns gray upon exposure to light.

Cyanoacrylate, or superglue vapours, react with water and other fingerprint constituents to form a hard, whitish deposit. Modern labs and criminal investigations also employ lasers and alternative light sources to view latent fingerprints. The FBI first used these techniques in 1978. Since lasers can damage the retina, special precautions are necessary.

The Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS): AFIS is a computerized system designed to store and retrieve finger-prints. First time it was established in the 1970s, AFIS was made to help the legal machinery and police officials to research extensive databases for a set of fingerprints taken from an individual and compare them to a single print, usually a latent print developed from a crime scene. By the 1990s, most large jurisdictions had implemented their own systems. However, a significant issue arose: a person's fingerprints might be in one AFIS database but not in others. In Pakistan, NADRA (National Database and Registration Authority) created a national database, linking the fingerprints of all computerized identity card holders centrally. This national database includes all 10-print cards from across the country, facilitating the identification of individuals nationwide.

Biometrics: In this modern world it is common that state departments use some human body prints or metrics for identification purposes (The Bertillon system may actually have been the first biometric system) Presently with a combination of AFIS. Examples are the introduction of a biometric system in education and judicial departments installed for attendance of employees. Biometrics can be utilized to control access to computers and other structures, identify individuals for security purposes, and help prevent identity theft and social services fraud. Fingerprints can be collected and stored on various surfaces, including porous ones like paper, cloth, and wood, as well as non-porous surfaces like glass and metal.

Recognition, Collection, and Preservation of Fingerprint Evidence:

- Fingerprints are some of the most reliable and probative forms of physical evidence.
- Objects suspected to have latent prints should be collected intact and submitted to the laboratory's latent print section for examination.
- If collecting objects is impractical or impossible, latent print development must be performed at the scene using methods such as tape lifting or photography. Like other types of evidence, fingerprint evidence must be carefully documented, and the chain of custody must be maintained.

System for Latent Print Analysis: The ACE-V method is used to analyze latent prints. This involves determining the correct location of the print, identifying any color issues or other unusual circumstances, and deciding on the print's suitability for analysis.

Evaluation/comparison with a Known Sample Involves More than a few Levels:

1. The general flow and pattern of the ridges must be examined.
2. The specific ridge characteristics and their locations are compared.
3. The shape, location, number, and relationships of pores, as well as the shape and size of edge features, are analyzed.

During this comparison process if any type of unexplained difference occurred it will lead to conclusion that the known sample is excluded as the source of the latent print. If all compared features match the known sample and there are enough unique features when considered together, individualization can be concluded. Peer review of the comparison further solidifies the conclusion of individualization. Generally, 8-12 points of comparison are considered sufficient, though no specific number is set.

Evaluations: Inadequate edge detail to form a decision can result in either exclusion or individualization.

Gender base Identification of Forensic fingerprints: Gender-based fingerprint identification refers to the concept of determining an individual's gender based on the analysis of their fingerprint patterns. This field of study explores whether there are distinct differences in fingerprint characteristics that correlate with the gender of a person (Sodhi, G. S., & Kaur 2005). Here are the key aspects and advancements in gender-based fingerprint identification includes:

Fingerprint Patterns: Research has indicated that females generally have higher ridge densities (more ridges per unit area) than males. The distribution of fingerprint pattern types (loops, whorls, arches) can vary between genders, although these differences are often subtle.

Statistical Analysis:

- Statistical methods are used to analyse the morphological features of fingerprints, such as ridge count, ridge thickness, and minutiae points, to identify gender-specific trends.
- Models are developed to estimate the probability that a given fingerprint belongs to a male or female based on these features.

Machine Learning and AI: Machine learning algorithms can be trained to discern gender-specific characteristics in fingerprints. Deep learning models, including convolutional neural networks (CNNs), are capable of automatically extracting features from fingerprint images and accurately classifying them by gender (Sodhi, G. S., & Kaur, 2005).

Enhanced Imaging Techniques and its Application:

- Advanced scanning technologies capture fingerprints in greater detail, allowing for more precise analysis of ridge patterns and minutiae.
- 3D fingerprint scanning provides additional depth information, which can help in distinguishing gender-related features more accurately.
- Gender-based fingerprint identification can assist in narrowing down suspects in a criminal investigation
- It can be useful in identifying the gender of unknown victims based on fingerprint evidence.
- Incorporating gender identification into biometric systems can provide an additional layer of security and personalization (Sodhi, G. S., & Kaur 2005).

Accuracy Challenges and Reliability Consideration:

- **Variability:** There is significant variability in fingerprint patterns within genders, and overlapping characteristics can make gender determination challenging.
- The potential for false positives (incorrectly identifying gender) and false negatives (failing to identify gender) must be carefully managed.

Standardization and Protocols:

Developing standardized protocols for gender-based fingerprint identification to ensure consistency and reliability across different applications and jurisdictions.

Traditional Fingerprint Analysis: Several high-profile cases have demonstrated the power of fingerprint evidence. For instance, the conviction of the infamous "Night

Stalker" Richard Ramirez in 1985 heavily relied on a single fingerprint left on a window screen. Similarly, the 1999 case of the murder of Hae Min Lee, which gained widespread attention through the podcast "Serial," saw fingerprints as a crucial element in the investigative process. These cases underscore the traditional strength of fingerprint analysis in forensic investigations (Jones, 2021).

Challenges faced by Forensic Science: Despite its historical successes, fingerprint analysis is not without its challenges. The inherent variability in fingerprint quality due to environmental factors or deliberate tampering can compromise the reliability of evidence. For instance, in the 2004 Madrid train bombings, Brandon Mayfield, an American attorney, was wrongfully detained due to an erroneous fingerprint match. This high-profile error highlighted the potential for mistakes even in a well-regarded system (Sodhi, G. S., & Kaur 2005).

Advancements in Fingerprint Obfuscation: Criminals have become increasingly sophisticated in evading fingerprint detection. Techniques such as skin grafting, chemical alterations, and abrasion can significantly alter fingerprint patterns. A notorious example is the case of John Dillinger, a 1930s gangster who underwent surgery to erase his fingerprints. In contemporary times, more advanced methods, such as the application of corrosive substances, have been employed by criminals to obliterate their prints, posing significant challenges for forensic experts.

Digital Age and Fingerprints: The digital age has introduced a new dimension to fingerprint analysis: digital fingerprints. Unlike physical fingerprints, digital fingerprints refer to the unique traces of activity left by individuals on electronic devices. Cybercriminals, for example, can leave behind digital fingerprints that forensic analysts can trace to uncover identities and track illegal activities. However, these digital traces are often encrypted or deliberately obfuscated, presenting new challenges in the field of digital forensics.

Case Study: The Silk Road Investigation: The takedown of the Silk Road, a notorious online black market, highlights the complexities and potential of digital fingerprint analysis. Ross Ulbricht, the founder of the Silk Road, was identified and arrested in part due to digital forensic techniques that traced his online activities back to him. This case exemplifies how digital fingerprints can be as critical as physical ones in solving modern crimes, yet it also showcases the sophisticated measures criminals take to conceal their digital trails.

The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Modern Forensics: Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) are transforming forensic science, offering tools that enhance the analysis of both physical and digital fingerprints. AI can process and compare vast databases of fingerprints with unprecedented speed and accuracy, reducing the margin of error and increasing the likelihood of accurate matches. For instance, the FBI's Next Generation Identification (NGI) system uses advanced algorithms to improve the precision of fingerprint matches, significantly enhancing investigative capabilities in USA (Smith, J. D., & Johnson 2020).

Case Study: The Use of AI in Cold Cases: AI's impact is particularly notable in revisiting cold cases. The Golden State Killer, a serial murderer and rapist who evaded capture for decades, was finally apprehended in 2018 using genetic genealogy and advanced forensic techniques, including AI-driven fingerprint analysis. This case underscores the potential of AI to breathe new life into unsolved cases, providing justice long after traditional methods have failed (Smith, J. D. 2021).

Challenges in Implementing Advanced Technologies: Despite the promise of AI and ML, integrating these technologies into forensic science presents its own challenges.

Issues such as algorithmic bias, data privacy concerns, and the need for extensive training and resources can hinder the adoption of these advanced tools. Moreover, the legal system's pace of adapting to technological advancements often lags, raising questions about the admissibility and interpretation of AI-derived evidence in court.

Case Study: Algorithmic Bias in Forensic AI: A pertinent example of the challenges posed by AI is the controversy surrounding facial recognition technology, which shares similarities with fingerprint analysis. Studies have shown that facial recognition systems can exhibit biases, particularly against people of color. These biases can lead to wrongful identifications and convictions, as seen in the cases of Robert Williams and Michael Oliver, who were wrongfully arrested due to faulty facial recognition matches. These incidents highlight the critical need for transparency and bias mitigation in forensic AI systems (Smith, J. D., & Johnson 2020).

Future Directions and Ethical Considerations: The future of fingerprint analysis and forensic science lies in the integration of advanced technologies with traditional methods. This hybrid approach can address current challenges and improve the accuracy and reliability of forensic evidence. However, it is crucial to balance technological advancements with ethical considerations. Ensuring that AI systems are free from bias, protecting individual privacy, and establishing clear guidelines for the use of forensic technology are imperative steps.

Case Study: The Ethical Implications of Genetic Fingerprinting:

The use of genetic fingerprinting in the Golden State Killer case raised significant ethical questions. While the technique was instrumental in solving the case, it also sparked debate over privacy concerns and the potential misuse of genetic data (Smith, J. D., & Johnson 2020). The balance between solving crimes and protecting individual rights remains a delicate issue, necessitating ongoing dialogue and regulation. Fingerprint analysis continues to be a vital tool in forensic science, but it faces significant challenges from evolving criminal tactics and technological advancements. The integration of AI and digital forensic techniques offers promising solutions, yet also introduces new complexities and ethical considerations. By examining case studies and addressing these emerging challenges, the forensic community can adapt and enhance its methodologies, ensuring that fingerprint analysis remains a robust tool in the fight against crime.

5. Relevant Pakistani Case Laws

PLJ 2019 Lahore 68: According to Article 84 of the Qanun-e-Shahadat Order, 1984 (Act No. X of 1984), the court is authorized to compare the signature or thumb impression of any individual. This provision allows the court to provide specific instructions to the trial court regarding such comparisons. The dismissal of the writ petition indicates that the higher court found no irregularities or illegalities committed by the lower courts in this regard. 2012 SCMR 1258, 1980 SCMR 557, 1991 SCMR 970, PLD 2006 Lah. 738, 2015 SCMR 284 & 2016 YLR 251 ref.

PLJ 2019 Lahore 68: Mr. Muhammad Masood Bilal, Advocate for Petitioner.

Date of hearing: 12.11.2018. Order: In the course of a specific performance suit initiated by the petitioner/plaintiff, the petitioner filed an application to send the signatures of Respondent No. 4 to a fingerprint expert for comparison. This application was contested by the respondents/defendants. The trial court, in an order dated March 2, 2018, dismissed the application. The petitioner, dissatisfied with this decision, filed a civil revision before the

Revisional Court, which was subsequently disposed of with directions to the trial court in an order dated September 17, 2018. Feeling aggrieved by these orders, the petitioner has now filed the present writ petition.

In a relevant case law (**2012 SCMR 1258**), the Honorable court emphasized that expert opinions are binding on courts and must be considered in making decisions.

Another case (**2010 M L D 1745**) discussed the application of Qanun-e-Shahadat (Order No. X of 1984) and the Specific Relief Act (Act No. I of 1877) in a situation involving an agreement to sell. The High Court directed the son of the executants, who were permanently settled abroad and elderly, to obtain specimen signatures and thumb impressions verified by the Consulate of Pakistan. These documents were to be submitted to the Trial Court for comparison with the agreement to sell and receipt. The Trial Court was instructed to seek the opinion of handwriting and fingerprint experts before deciding the case anew in accordance with the law.

6. Conclusion

It is an old but most authentic source of identification of victim and offender. This area of Forensic needs development and further improvement and training because NADRA has record of almost all citizens fingerprint if could be utilized in crime investigation will be very helpful. Gender-based fingerprint identification remains a developing field with promising potential applications in forensics, security, and beyond. However, it also requires careful consideration of ethical, legal, and technical challenges to ensure its responsible and effective use.

Suggestions/Recommendations:

Researcher suggest following measures should be taken to cover gaps in technology for futer betterment:

- Automated Fingerprint Identification Systems (AFIS): Implementing and upgrading AFIS with enhanced algorithms for better accuracy and speed in matching fingerprints.
- Utilizing high-resolution scanners and advanced imaging software to capture and enhance fingerprints.
- Incorporating 3D scanning technology to capture more detailed ridge patterns and surface features.
- Providing ongoing training for forensic professionals on the latest techniques and technologies.
- Establishing and maintaining certification programs to ensure analysts are proficient in current methodologies.
- Adopting and adhering to international standards and protocols, such as those provided by organizations like ISO.
- Implementing rigorous quality control measures and regular audits to maintain high standards in fingerprint analysis.
- Promoting collaboration between forensic laboratories, academic institutions, and technology companies to drive innovation.
- Developing interoperable systems that allow for seamless sharing of fingerprint data between jurisdictions and countries.
- Enhancing centralized databases to include more comprehensive and accessible fingerprint records.
- Ensuring that fingerprint data is stored and used in compliance with privacy laws and security protocols.

- Keeping forensic practices aligned with current legal standards and addressing any legal challenges related to the use of fingerprint evidence.
- Incorporating AI and machine learning to improve the accuracy of fingerprint matching and to identify patterns that may not be immediately obvious to human analysts.
- Using predictive analytics to anticipate and identify trends in fingerprint analysis.
- Participating in and organizing international conferences, workshops, and forums to share knowledge and advancements.
- Establishing agreements and partnerships between countries for mutual assistance and data sharing in forensic investigations.
- Single national data bank of Fingerprint should be formulated to make Investigation more powerful.
- Data for data bank should be gathered by internet link which should be connected with each corner of Pakistan and where ever anyone scan his thumb and use biometric system his/her prints with identification should be collected.
- Artificial Intelligence should be used to get quick results for matching fingerprints.

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